

Rational Games Transcript

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FN: Might I ask how you got to Rational Games?

JW: So, for me it started because I was a participant at one of Rational Games' seminars. So I had a scholarship at the German Studentenstiftung des Deutschen Volkes and Mark had been teaching there for several years. And when I attended the seminar, it was a three-day seminar in Weimar, I noticed that in three days straight I hadn't looked at **MY** watch a single time. And I was like, that must have been a pretty good seminar. So, after the seminar I walked up to Mark and asked him if I could perhaps do an internship at Rational Games. And at the time I was still a bachelor's student. And then he was like, yeah, if you're doing well, perhaps you can become a trainer. And since then, yeah, he's been building me up. And I've been teaching with Rational Games now for three and a half years. (...)

FN: What was your inspiration to start Rational Games and what is the concept behind your method?

MY: For me it was kind of a midlife project. I spent 14 years in the business world doing various things. And then took a sabbatical and did a PhD in Germany. And as part of that I was at Harvard for a year. And as I was finishing up and thinking what I would do next, I realized I wanted to do something entrepreneurial. And so, I and a friend decided we would found a company called Rational Games. Rational because we're serious, Games because we're fun. And that we would teach negotiation, which is what I've been doing all **MY** life. And we would teach it with playful methods. We don't use PowerPoint, we don't use "frontal unterricht. But it's experiential. We do theater techniques, we do simulations, sometimes we dance. We do all sorts of interesting things. So that was founded in 2001.

What is perhaps of interest, and we've taught all over the world, 40 countries around the world. Not only on Zoom, also live. The last one was Albania, that was fun. And we teach in Germany for the foreign ministry, the new diplomats. We coach one of the parties in the Bundestag. We work with CEOs, with startups, with foundations, NGOs. Lots of people. Anyone that wants to negotiate playfully to get to a win-win result. We have nine trainers, Julian is one. And the freelance, we are a consulting company. So that's how we earn money. What's perhaps interesting is that we are also a social business. We are a registered non-profit in the US and in Germany. We will shortly be a "Stiftung", a German foundation. And because we set aside a large portion of what we earn doing this to support projects that use games and play to resolve conflict.

It's sort of a Robin Hood idea. We are using games and play to teach senior people how to negotiate. And then we are turning around and using that to support projects that do that creatively in the non-profit world. Things like soccer in Africa for kids to come together and play soccer. We have an ice hockey project in East Berlin. It's a former GDR athlete. He was six when he was swimming for the GDR, now he's 50. So, he has founded

something

47 called "Kick on Ice". They pick up the problem kids in the bad
48 neighborhoods of Berlin. Take them to the stadium and teach them ice
hockey.

49 They learn fair play. They learn to put their aggression into a puck and
50 not into a knife. We work with musicians without borders. We work with the
51 Help Alliance Lufthansa. We have all sorts of projects all over the world.
52 And we've given away a million dollars, which is a lot for us. Not so much
53 in the philanthropy world. We're working on increasing that. But that is
54 why we do what we do.

55 **FN:** How did the idea develop that this method of teaching has its
56 advantages and could have a market value?

57 **MY:** Organically is the first answer. It just sort of grew. My PhD had been
58 with game theory. It was very cerebral at first. Games in the sense of... And
59 we quickly got out of our heads and began to think about games that were
60 playful and not always brain games. I did a TEDx talk, which you can find
61 on the internet, called "The Urge to Play is Greater than the Urge to Fight."
62 We really believe that the "2spiel", the urge to play in people, is at least
63 as strong as the urge to fight. And so, our big idea is to combine those
64 and to combat the urge to fight with the urge to play. So, if we get people
65 to be playful, then it reduces conflict, it reduces violence. And they
66 learn a lot more. You learn more in a seminar if you're playing than if
67 you're listening to PowerPoint. So, we thought that was a good idea. So, we
68 started with that. And I would say that it certainly is true.

69 **JW:** Even very serious people enjoy playing.

70 **MY:** Especially very serious people. I'm dying to play.

71 **JW:** You would be surprised with the diplomats. Some of them really like
72 playing an opera singer. And they play it so well they get a bottle of wine
73 afterwards. (...)

74 **M:** No, it's, we just think that it's a more pleasant way to get through
75 life. You learn a lot more and it resolves conflict. We're amazed by the,
76 we've managed, we've taught all kinds of thousands of people by now. And
77 I've taught, you know, bureaucrats in Bonn and at the Deutsche Telekom.
78 I've taught Stadtwerke in Münster. I've taught around the world and with
79 very, very few exceptions. They like to play. If you give them a safe space
80 so that it is not difficult for them, then they do open up and that's
81 always very beautiful to see.

82 **FN:** Looking at your very broad spectrum of actors and clients that you
work
83 with and the wide systemic shifts that we have or experience in Europe
84 right now from the social problems that we're facing, migration, climate,
85 all of these big topics that we're discussing now. What do you think has
86 the greatest impact on the way we negotiate these, or we change the way
we
87 negotiate issues of this scale?

88 **JW:** I would answer quite plainly, I think, with the Harvard principle to
89 separate the people from the problem. I've seen the power of that and I've
90 also seen the opposite, if you're not able to do that. So, I think in

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91 everyday political negotiations, people often create problems around
 92 wanting to be seen, wanting to have influence, or feeling hurt or
 93 disregarded. And I think if you're able to move that out of the way,
 94 because you put the interests, the common interests, like for example when
 95 you talk about negotiating for climate and the environment to preserve
 96 basically the basis of human life on earth, if you have that very strong
 97 interest that every party should have and that every party can sell to
 98 their constituencies, you put that at the core, and the people know that
 99 it's about this and they can go home to their home front and present to
 100 them we've all agreed on this issue, instead of this guy didn't agree and
 101 wants to be seen and disregarded me and so now I have to fight back. I
 102 think if you talk people to people and put relationships first and
 103 interests first, that's the most powerful way to go.

104 **MY:** And I think an example of this ridiculous fight between Musk and
 105 Trump
 106 that's in all the papers this morning, is all about revenge and personal
 107 power and there's absolutely nothing about issues there. It's all about
 108 throwing smoke bombs back and forth and you have to get out of that
 109 mode.
 108 Unfortunately, he is President of the United States, I'm afraid, but I wish
 109 we could teach him a thing or two.

110 **FN:** Did you maybe notice in the 24 years of Rational Games the shift in the
 111 way we negotiate things in Europe and Germany?

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112 **MY:** We've worked for three years with one of the parties in the Bundestag
 113 and I can speak for that and I really do think we've changed the mindset
 114 because one of the things we teach is that you want to be empathetic, you
 115 want to find out what the other side really wants, what's in there is what
 116 we call their iceberg, and that that's the place to start instead of
 117 lecturing and telling them arguments as to why you're right. Instead, you
 118 let them tell you what matters to them and you work with that. And in our
 119 work with that party at many levels, we have made that change. I can say
 120 that when the 21 elections came along in Germany, I was given the strategy
 121 papers for the election and I can't tell you much about them, but I will
 122 tell you that two-thirds of it was our stuff. So, stuff that we had said,
 123 you need to listen, you need to ask questions, came straight from us and it
 124 was in their strategy paper. And that I think was one of the most important
 125 revelations of my professional life was to see, wow, we really made an
 126 impact with somebody that has power. So that was great.

127 **FN:** That's fascinating. Maybe also inside the political sphere, but also
 128 outside of the political sphere, have you been involved in the negotiations
 129 in any kind yourself besides teaching? Can you tell me about the most
 130 demanding negotiation and what made it work or what didn't make it work
 131 in
 the end?

..3.1.1. Challenges

132 **MY:** A lot of that is confidential, so I can't really speak to it here. But
 133 I will say that the hardest thing is your partner negotiating at home. It's
 134 the hardest thing you'll ever do with climate change or anything else
 135 because you know each other so well and all these personal, emotional
 136 things can come into play. So that is where I'm still fighting after all
 137 this time, having told everyone else how to do it. But yeah, I mean, our
 138 role normally is advising. We don't always go to the table. We help to

..3.1.1. Challenges

139 prepare. We help to debrief. And we coach fairly senior people on how to
140 negotiate better. So, I can see what the result is. But we don't appear in
141 the press or anything like that.

142 **FN:** What do you have in mind?

..3.1.1. Challenges

143 **J:** I do as well, but I would also not go into detail. I've been involved
144 with some multilateral negotiations and I think the most challenging of
145 that is communications because there is so much going on at the same
time.

..3.1.1. Challenges

146 So, at one point I was wondering if in this very complex multilateral
147 negotiation situation, you are really still negotiating or if you are not
148 just updating each other. Because there is so much time being used up by
149 stating positions that you don't even have time anymore for asking
150 questions. I think that's blocking the progress a lot. When you have all
151 the parties sitting in the room and you go through the text and you have
152 the brackets there and it takes up days and nights and everybody is tired
153 and everybody is exhausted and then in comes new information on several
154 topics and several work streams at the same time. So, I think this is one
155 of the biggest challenges perhaps.

..2.2. Non-European

156 **MY:** I could also add I was a trade negotiator for the first George Bush.
157 Not the son, but the father. I was two years in negotiating services,
158 trading services, which was at the time trying to create a trading services
159 around the GATT. But also, by that I'm talking to the French about
160 broadcasting, talking to the Japanese about landing rights for airlines,
161 talking to the Taiwanese about insurance licenses. Maybe not so sexy, but
162 it's more than half the economy. There I got some real experience in seeing
163 that and I would [looking to Julian] agree with you that there is an awful
164 lot of gaslighting, a lot of talking, especially in certain cultures. They
165 are known for just talking, talking, talking. And it is all as what we
166 would call positions and not interests. They are not telling what they care
167 about. They are reciting something that they demand that you are never
168 going to give them. It's about breaking through that and getting underneath
169 that. And that's often done away from the table, especially when
170 multilateral. I mean it's done over coffee in the foyer, it's done at lunch,
171 it's done having a walk where you really get underneath the official
172 positions, which are not that important. What's important is interests. And
173 relationships. And values. (...)

..5.1. Essential Skill:

..5.4. Lessons Learned

174 **FN:** So pretty much the idea is to say, okay, if we have like in a formal
175 way, we only state the positions, we only see the positions, so we go into
176 the informal connection to the people and get into the interest values.

177 **FN:** And we do that with case studies.

178 **MY:** We do several multilateral case studies, especially in the diplomatic
179 world. And they learn that we have a meeting at the table, everybody says
180 their position, everybody says no. And then we have a half-hour break and
181 they talk to each other, and they come back and now one or two people say
182 yes. And then we have another break and it all happens away from the
table.

183 The meetings at the table are not that important.

184 **FN:** But do you think they're necessary?

185 **MY:** It's part of the game. It's part of the procedure.

186 **JW:** And also, what makes it official. Yeah, you need the effort to do it. (.
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188 **FN:** Having this experience, especially with the informal, and the bridge
189 between what we research, what we do, what we know, what do you feel at
the
190 moment, especially in the European context, is the biggest gap between the
191 research, the practice, and maybe the civil society that is looking at the
192 negotiations or the outcome?

193 **JW:** So, I would say in my Masters I studied international relations and
194 diplomacy, so I read quite a lot on diplomatic negotiations. I think once
195 you enter the professional field, you notice you just don't have time for
196 reading anymore. Not academic articles. You're so caught up in reading the
197 news and reading analysis and everything. So, I think the biggest gap,
198 possibly from my personal experience at least, is those two ivory towers
199 standing next to each other, the professional world, and the academic
world,
200 and how to bridge the very complex writings sometimes of the academic
201 world to make them accessible.

202 **MY:** Which is designed to be not accessible. And how do you make it
clear?

203 **JW:** And I think that's what this conference is all about. Because we're in the
204 Sorbonne, this is one of the major academic institutions. We have a lot of,
205 I haven't seen the list, but I assume lots of professors. But we also have
206 people like me. I'm not a professor. I'm a practitioner.

207 **JW:** You're a doctor now.

208 **MY:** Well, okay. So that's the idea, to connect practitioners with academics,
209 which is sorely needed, I think.

210 **FN:** Beside these kinds of conferences, where you can have a personal
211 connection between practitioners and research, would you have an idea
how
212 to bridge it, or how in your practice would like research to be integrated
213 with, so it's more and easily accessible for you?

214 **MY:** I've published a few articles, also in the Harvard Journal. And I
215 deliberately don't make them academic. I don't do a lot of footnotes. I
216 don't do a lot of, it's really essays, which is kind of what our blogs are
217 now. It's a much shorter version. And I find that that helps people to
218 understand things in a more normal way, even if it isn't peer-reviewed
219 academic work.

220 **JW:** I think another thing we do, which has worked pretty well, is podcasts.
221 So, there's a Rational Games podcast. Mark is moderating that podcast and
222 he interviews professionals in the field. And they share their experience
223 about negotiation.

224 **MY:** Well, I think it's quite a good idea because it came out of our team
225 that we're worried about how to get our brand up. Nobody knows who we
are.

226 So how do you make rational games known? And I've always resisted
227 putting
228 myself in the foreground and posting on Instagram what I had for breakfast.
229 I think that's nonsense. So, our idea was to find people who are more
230 important than us that do what we teach. And we have three topics. We
231 have
232 negotiation, that's our topic, gamification because we do it playfully, and
233 philanthropy because it's our social business. And we try to use those
234 three legs and invite reasonably famous people to talk to us. We've had
235 John Paul Lederach, who's a major peace researcher. We've had the head
236 of
237 the Kofi Annan Foundation in Geneva. We've had Hannah Riley Bowles, who
238 does a lot of general work at Harvard. We are now having another
239 gamification expert next week.

237 We do it every quarter. We've done this now for three or four years. We've
238 had 15 guests. And for me it's fascinating because you really do get to
239 have a conversation. We started putting it on Zoom. The idea was to make
240 it
241 interactive. We love to be interactive. And so, we thought we'd have a
242 Zoom,
243 not a webinar. I hate webinars. But a seminar. But that proved to be very,
244 very difficult because you get 120 registrations and 14 people show up.
245 And
246 that's a little "peinlich", as the Germans say. And so, we now do it
247 recorded. We do it as a podcast on Spotify. It's called the Powerhouse
248 Series.

246 **FN:** It's also like changing the medium. Going from these very exhausting
247 papers to a more approachable medium.

248 **MY:** I don't go to conferences anymore that are purely academic. I tried for
249 a while. I don't do well at them. I don't relate well to people. This one
250 is interesting because it's a mix.

251 **FN:** Okay. That's a fascinating point. I mean, this is pretty much also our
252 idea with the journal. And to think about going into other media would be,
253 of course, super interesting. Though I'm afraid of doing podcasts, they are
254 very long.

255 **MY:** Ours are short. They're like 30, 40 minutes. I always think the problem
256 with podcasts is they're always an hour, two hours. I don't have time to
257 listen to that for two hours. But at 30 minutes, I can do.

258 **JW:** You can do that while cooking, for example.

259 **MY:** So, we keep it to 30 minutes as parameters. We keep it to a period.
260 We'll talk for an hour, but then we'll cut it to 40 minutes.

261 **FN:** Thinking about all the people you talked with already and the clients
262 you had? Did you notice specific ways the Europeans negotiate either with
263 each other or outside? And that is different from clients and experiences
264 you had on other parts of the planet.

265 **MY:** Culture is a very – we do a whole course in intercultural negotiation.
266 I wouldn't say so much within Europe. I mean, there are very different

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..5.3. Teaching Method | 314
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cultures, but there's a fundamental shared value, I think, in Europe that makes it easier. When you're dealing with the Russians or the Chinese or the Americans, there are larger differences, in style as well. And there's lots of research being done about what culture is. First of all, culture is not only countries. It's not only Germany versus France. It's women versus men. It's journalists versus professors. Those are all cultures. And you are a member of five or six cultures all at once. So, it's a complicated question.

FN: Yes, absolutely.

MY: But I would say when you leave Europe, it gets more interesting. When you're dealing with Indians and Chinese, that's when you run into some larger cultural differences.

JW: I would think spontaneously that there's three main aspects that make a difference. One would be communication style, so high context or low context. Second would be the importance of relationships. So, if you're just getting together to do business, or if you need to get to know each other for a couple of weeks, months, or years to develop a base of trust. And then negotiate. A great example is ambassadors in China, for example, that are invited to have tea several times. Only having tea, only talking about tea. Several weeks before the first time, they talk about actual issues. At least that's what I've been told by some professionals from the field. It's not my personal experience. But that's certainly a difference. Certainly, in the EU, you would sit down and negotiate right from the start, after you've had a coffee and said hello and shook hands. Especially in Germany.

And the third line, I would say, is context of the historical events. So, I think in Europe, you do have the context, that is what Mark said, the uniting context that you want to make this project work. I think many European diplomats and politicians still remember that Europe used to be in constant state of conflict. For centuries. And these days, it's really important to stick together and to make it work. And then if you go to the Global South, for example, you have still this post-colonial context. So, you still have this Global South, Global North divide. When you look at the North, you just think they're frugal. And they always make these promises, but they're not paying. And so, if you talk with each other, you always have to have in mind what is the historical lens that this person is situated in.

FN: From this perspective and your experience, and for yourself, thinking about intercultural negotiation or doing negotiation outside of Europe, is there something where you were like, okay, this is something I learn from that. This is something I saw, for example, in Vietnam, and I am absolutely a fan of this, and I integrate it into my own negotiation.

MY: Yes, anecdotes. Everyone has a funny story of something cultural. And it's not always verbal. It's body language and gestures that mean very different things in very different cultures. As trainers, we learn to be careful with that. So, it's about being sensitive, doing your research, asking ChatGPT what to do, and trying not to make stupid mistakes, and being attuned to the fact that it is a different culture. We like to play the Barnga game. It's one of our favorite games. We do it in intercultural

316 seminars. We'll do it this week, next week. And what it is, it's a card
317 game. You put people at tables, and they all have a deck of cards, and they
318 play a trick, and they all get instructions. They can't speak. And the
319 instructions all look the same, but they're not the same because each table
320 has a different rule. One table says, Ace always wins. Next table says,
321 Only hearts win. Next table says, you have to have three of a kind. And so,
322 you just throw the cards, and then everybody understands the rule, and
323 then they pick up the trick. You do that for a while, and then you have one
324 person stand up, go to the next table, and keep playing. And they do what
325 they did before, but they don't win, even though it's an Ace. They don't
326 win, and they get upset, emotional. And so then after a while, when you do
327 this five, six times, everyone in the room is confused because who made the
328 rules here? The point is very obvious, but you have to know what the rules
329 are. And we don't know the rules, we make mistakes. It's an example of a
330 very experiential way.

..5.3. Teaching Methodoc

331 **JW:** It also means that different places have different sets of rules. And I
332 think that's very powerful also for the multilateral view. Like in New York,
333 you would definitely have a different kind of informal gatherings than,
334 for example, in Nairobi. I can tell from that experience that it's very,
335 very open. And the diplomatic community there is meeting a lot informally,
336 and just having a coffee together, going out in the evening together. I
337 would think that in New York or Geneva or in Brussels, they also have
338 unique circles of people, but those circles have a different culture. And I
339 think the place really influences that. In Finland, they go to the sauna. I
340 would prefer that.

..2.2. Non-European

341 **MY:** That's what Kohl did with Jelzin, very famously. For German unity,
342 Helmut Kohl, the chancellor, was in the sauna, naked, with Jelzin. And
343 that's how they made a deal about whether they could keep the military in
344 Germany or not. So, knowing the rules, being aware of where you are, and
345 being pretty much authentic, as I feel. And empathetic. Not imposing what
346 you think the rules are on everybody else.

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..5.4. Lessons Learn

347 **JW:** And respectful. I think also for the different cultural norms and
348 values.

349 **FN:** When you don't win the game?

350 **JW:** Well, that's a good question. What does it mean to win the game?
351 What
352 does winning mean? That's where we can talk about finite and infinite
353 games,
354 right? You know, Simon Sinek wrote on that.

353 **MY:** Do you know about that? Well, it started, there was a book in the 70s,
354 a small philosophy book called Finite and Infinite Games. And Simon Sinek
355 picked it up last year, and he had a bestseller about the application of
356 the business world. And the idea is that life is a game, and we think that
357 too. But there are finite games and there are infinite games. Finite games
358 have rules. They have a beginning and an end. They have a winner and a
359 loser. And you want to win against the other side. Like soccer. Or chess.
360 Or most games that we know.

..5.1. Essential Skills

..5.1. Essential Skills

361 An infinite game has no beginning and no end. There is no winner or loser.
362 It's just the joy of playing. And you play to keep playing. And that's what
363 we try to do. It's an abstract idea, but you can bring it to life. You
364 don't always have to win. Everybody can win. Even win-win, it's an archaic
365 word. Win-win. Just get rid of win. There's no win. It's enjoying. It's
366 related. I don't know what else. Develop.

367 **JW:** Grow together.

368 **MY:** Negotiation is competitive and cooperative. We like to use the
metaphor
369 of capoeira, which is Brazilian. Because it's a fight, but it's also a
370 dance. So, we talk a lot about negotiation as a dance. It has choreography.
371 It's fun. It's beautiful. But it has an edge to it.

372 **FN:** When I teach music to young people, I always explain that it's playing
373 an instrument. It's not learning an instrument. You play it, find out what
374 you like, find out what sounds well. In **MY** brain, I always think that's an
375 infinite game that I'm playing for a while. In your experience and what you
376 teach in your format, what do you feel is a key skill that you add to your
377 clients? That they learn afterwards and are like, okay, this is how I'm
378 going to approach things.

..5.1. Essential Skills

379 **MY:** Awareness. Definitely awareness. Seeing things, noticing things. Being
380 aware of what you're doing, being aware of your style, knowing whether
you
381 should change it. It's sharpening awareness, which is a major source of
382 power.

..5.1. Essential Skills

383 **JW:** I would say strategic exploration. Learning to ask questions the right
384 way, learning to listen, and then preparing strategically.

385 **MY:** We do a lot of preparation. That's a big thing.

..5.1. Essential Skills

386 **JW:** Because I think many negotiators don't know that you can actually
387 prepare very well and very strategically for negotiations. Obviously, you
388 don't follow the plan, agenda item by agenda item. You improvise. You still
389 need to keep it up in the air. But if you have the right building blocks
390 prepared, I think that also makes you much more flexible.

391 **MY:** That's, to me, one of the central dilemmas. We really like preparation.
392 We teach them a very structured way to do it. We want them to spend one
393 hour preparing if they're one hour negotiating. We really drill this in our
394 seminars. But we also want them not to fall in love with their preparation.
395 If they hear something that they didn't know, to immediately drop it and
396 listen. That's the great art, to be prepared but to be also improvisational.

397 **FN:** From my experience, it's usually easier to improvise when I'm prepared.

398 **MY:** You know what you're leaving behind.

399 **FN:** Do I understand it right that it's more really introspective where
400 people look inside themselves, be aware of what they're doing and then
401 start to look outside?

..5.1. Essential Skills

402 **JW:** It has both sides to it. You've got to be aware of what you want and
403 what your priorities are in the interests you've identified in yourself and
404 the parties you are negotiating for. But then you've also got to be aware
405 of your counterpart. And that you only get by asking questions, by asking
406 others questions, perhaps listening in, and then exploring. And also,
407 obviously exploring third parties as well that are always included in the
408 deal. So, it's both introspective and also the other direction that you
409 find out more about the setting you're going to negotiate in and the
410 interests that are involved.

..5.1. Essential Skills

411 **MY:** And it's a mindset shift because we don't really think that much about
412 other people. We don't. We go through life focused on ourselves. How am I
413 feeling? What's for lunch? What's out the window? I'm very focused on
414 everything about me and I don't even listen. So, to get away from that I
415 really have a curiosity, which can be trained, that you really want to know
416 why do they behave that way? Why is Donald Trump this way – what is that
417 all about? Without judgment, without trying to defeat him, but to just
418 understand what would make someone behave that way. And then how do I
419 deal
420 with that? We don't have a chance to talk to Donald Trump, but someone
421 needs to. He's very needy. I think more and more he's needy. He is like a
422 child. He doesn't feel loved. I really think that's the problem.

422 **JW:** That's his deepest interest. It is. That's him. Being seen, going down
423 in history. Having the Nobel Prize. Being recognized as the greatest
424 negotiator of all time. Dealmaker.

425 **MY:** Having feedback, having validation by other people.

426 **FN:** I remember this sentence in Siddhartha from Herman Hesse. There was
427 this one sentence: "People are children." Which really stuck with me. For
428 me this explains all the games, this explains all the hurt that we develop
429 when we're getting older.

..5.1. Essential Skills

430 **JW:** It's like the inner child coming out in a conflict situation. I think
431 that's also another very interesting introspective layer in the
432 negotiations that we try to teach. Be aware of the dynamic that you're
433 getting into. Because you can't prepare as much as you want to. Sometimes
434 you're getting in a situation and then your counterpart doesn't do what you
435 would like them to do. Or triggers something in you, some neural networks
436 that make you behave in a different way than you want it to. And you kind
437 of lose sight of your initial goal. And you just get into an emotional
438 dynamic and you get out of it with something you really didn't want. And I
439 think that's another introspective layer that people should be more aware
440 of. The vertical.

441 **MY:** Systems thinking. It's all about things that create and they go faster
442 and faster and you can't control. You see it all the time.

443 **FN:** So, if you have the chance to choose a professor, maybe hear from the
444 conference, take them for like half an hour, what research question would
445 you like them to answer? What should be researched in the field of
446 negotiation? What appears dominant as a question that you have in your
447 mind
at the moment?

..6.1. Research Questic

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448 **MY:** You should ask some of them and they'll tell you. I strongly recommend
449 you talk to Remi [Smolinsky] if you haven't yet. He has a lot of
450 interesting ideas about what should be researched. I don't know. Why do
451 people not... Why are people so set on winning? What is this that we all
452 think we... You know, if you look at it from a distance - and I'm a
453 philosopher by training - you won the soccer game. You have two goals and
454 they have one and everyone is ecstatically happy. Why does that matter?
455 It's a ball and you reduce it to the physical. So, get people out of that
456 mindset. How do you do it? So, the research would be how do you do it
457 pedagogically? And what effects would it have? I think that's an
458 interesting question.

459 **JW:** I'm not so sure about what to ask, but definitely ask [incomp.] He can
460 tell you stories about everything. Because he's lived through some of the
461 major historical negotiations. And I think he has a very deep insight on
462 almost any topic.

463 **FN:** Maybe to close the interview here with the last question. This is also,
464 what I found out, the most difficult question for most of the people. But I
465 like it very much. If you think about a piece of media, a song, a movie, a
466 book, a theatre play, whatever comes to mind, that relates to negotiation,
467 what would you recommend to our readers? If you read that, if you see that,
468 hear that, you will have an impact on the way you negotiate or the way you
469 understand negotiation.

470 **MY:** I have an easy answer because I just had an experience last week. And
471 there is a song that is pretty cheesy actually. Cheesy? Pretty? And it was
472 done by the 12 tenors that I've seen. Which is the most of it. And it's
473 called You Raise Me Up. You Raise Me Up. And it's You Raise Me Up. When I
474 was down and you make me up. It's better than I ever could. And I think
475 that's what we're talking about. Raising your opponent up. Making them
476 look good. That is a mindset that changes a lot.

477 **JW:** So, I think the obvious starting point for everyone who is interested
478 in negotiating interest-based and opposition-based is Harvard's "Getting to
479 yes". I think that's a bit too easy of an answer. I think for me personally,
480 as part of my Masters, we also watched a movie. I don't remember its
481 name.

482 But it was about the negotiations between Kosovo and Serbia. It was a
483 British mediator who was trying to get both sides on the table. And you
484 really see the importance of relationships and setting. So, one little
485 aspect of it was that the mediator every day would wear a different funny
486 tie. And you can see in the movie how that sets the tone.

486 **MY:** Humor is so important.

487 **FN:** Perfect. Thank you so much. Is there anything that you feel like you
488 would like to tell us that came to your mind that didn't fit the questions?

489 **MY:** Things will get better. I believe that.